

EU Policy Brief

Hybrid Intelligence in Decision Systems

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1. ANALYSIS

Europe has built a strong [computing infrastructure](#) (e.g., high-performance computers) critical to AI's success. Europe also has sizable public and industrial data that isn't being used to its full potential. It has well-established industrial strengths in the production of safe and stable digital systems with low power consumption, which are critical for the advancement of AI. Leveraging the EU's capacity to invest in next-generation technologies and infrastructures, as well as digital competencies such as data-driven transformation and the data-agile economy will increase, Europe's technical sovereignty in key enabling technologies and infrastructures for the data economy. However, competitors such as China and the United States are now innovating rapidly and projecting their data access and usage ideas around the world. Therefore, strengthening the EU's role as a global actor, in addition to efforts in other domains, requires a unified and comprehensive approach to disruptive technologies.

Turning to [critical concerns raised by AI](#) stated by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence set up by the European Commission, it is worth mentioning the most important ones in order to understand the scope of the threat as follows:

- Prohibited AI practices, for instance, manipulate persons through subliminal techniques beyond their consciousness or exploit specific vulnerable groups, or manipulate the free choice, or biometric identification systems,

- High-risk AI systems such as an AI system intended to be used as a safety component of products that are subject to third party ex-ante conformity assessment,

- Covert AI systems that do not ensure that humans are made aware of – or able to request and validate the fact that – they interact with an AI system,

- Security vulnerabilities of algorithmic decision systems due to high complexity that malign actors can exploit,

- Lethal autonomous weapon systems with cognitive skills to decide whom, when and where to fight without human intervention.

To address these challenges of AI, hybrid intelligence could be a trustworthy and sustainable option. Hybrid intelligence refers to a perfect amalgam of human and artificial intelligence. Machine learning/artificial intelligence can make statistical inferences based on patterns found in previous cases and learning as the data input increases. Furthermore, such procedures allow the [detection of complex trends](#) in a model configuration as well as the interrelationships between single components, extending methods like simulations and scenarios. Still, they are unable to [predict soft and subjective assessments](#) of cases, such as the innovativeness of a value proposition, the vision or fit of the team, or the overall accuracy of a business model, which makes computer annotation of such data impossible.

Therefore, humans can become [the gold standard](#) for evaluating data that is difficult to annotate and train for machine learning models like creativity and innovation. Humans excel at making subjective judgments about data that is difficult to quantify objectively using statistical methods. Furthermore, human experts have well-organized domain expertise, allowing them to identify and interpret scarce data. On the other hand, as humans do have cognitive limitations, these can be mitigated through the hybrid intelligence process. This method combines the opinions of a wider community of people to minimize the noise and bias in individual assessments. Thus, by accessing more diverse domain information, incorporating it into an algorithm, and reducing the risk of biased interpretation, hybrid intelligence represents a proper way to supplement machine learning systems.

In other words, by integrating the complementary capabilities of humans and machines to produce superior results jointly and continually evolve by learning from each other, hybrid intelligence-powered decision support is highly likely to improve the outcomes of an individual's decision-making activities. Further, hybrid intelligence is used to take advantage of human wisdom while minimizing disadvantages of machines such as bias and random errors. Continuous human interaction with the proper interfaces speeds up the marking of complex or novel data that a computer can't handle, lowering the risk of data-related errors and automation biases.

2. POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

From the EU perspective, AI is a strategic technology that can contribute to the well-being of the people, businesses, and society as a whole if it is human-centric, ethical, and sustainable while still respecting fundamental rights and values. The European AI strategy aims to boost Europe's AI innovation potential while promoting the growth and adoption of ethical and trustworthy AI in the EU economy. The latest EU norms and regulations give particular emphasis on trustworthiness, explainability, accuracy, and human involvement. Yet, when it comes to decision support or algorithmic decision systems, it seems that the EU AI perspective needs to be reviewed with a hybrid intelligence approach. Although some terms such as "human-centric" or "human oversight" have already been highlighted in recent EU communications,

there is still a need for a deep understanding and comprehensive approach to utilizing hybrid intelligence-powered systems in Europe. In short, the EU must avoid operating an algorithmic black box inside what many in public perceive as the operational black box of the EU.

Therefore, the EU should seek to make increased use of hybrid intelligence in its internal processes and as an input to Commission decision-making and reviews of existing policy. To this end, the following policy recommendations to the EU are outlined as follows:

- A legislative framework for the governance of common European hybrid intelligence strategy and accordingly launching Hybrid Intelligence Act,

- Facilitate key enablers for investments in advanced human-machine interaction systems and strengthening Europe's capabilities and infrastructures for hosting, processing, and using human-in-the-loop and interoperability

- Invest in high impact projects on European hybrid intelligence strategy, encompassing data sharing and human-machine interaction architectures (including standards, best practices, tools) and governance mechanisms, as well as the European federation of trustworthy hybrid intelligence and related services

- Empower universities, labs, research centers, startups, and small-medium enterprises to invest in the use of hybrid intelligence and interoperability between humans and machines

- Add new project calls encouraging the use of hybrid intelligence to the Horizon Europe project portfolio.